

Financial Development and Foreign Direct Investment

Financial Development and Foreign Direct Investment in Belt and Road Initiative Economies- the Moderating Effect of Human Capital

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Abstract

This research aims to investigate the effect of financial development on foreign direct investment and the moderating effect of human capital in the relationship between financial development and foreign direct investment. The direct effect of human capital to foreign direct investment inflow has been found negative in earlier researches which is against common expectations. However, as human capital is an important part of financial sector of an economy, the moderation effect of these two is worth investigating. The research deploys sample dataset for 1999-2017 from 79 countries who are partners of Belt and Road Initiative. This sample is global representative as it contains a sample of diversified countries in terms of location, development stage and cultural traditions. The research employs fixed effect-random effect and feasible generalized least square modeling to investigate the issue. It is robustly found that while the moderating effect of human capital is considered, the negative effect of human capital to FDI fizzles out and significant positive effect of financial development and human capital on FDI emerges. Thus the policymakers of the region are suggested to concentrate on financial development and human capital development together to augment FDI attractiveness of the country for future.

Keywords: FDI, Financial Development, Human Capital, FGLS, FE-RE.

Introduction

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) have substantial influence on a developing country's external financing and economic growth, the manners of multinational corporations, and the extent of guideline of FDI and different forms of capital flows are some of the issues on which policy-makers ordinarily have to take a stand (De Gregorio, 2005). Generally speaking, FDI is locating investments abroad. The investing firm are multinational companies (MNCs) who invest their money to a country other than its home country while the recipient country is treated as host country (Yahia et al., 2018). To explain more formally, any investment from abroad to the host country firm which transfers the ownership of 10% or more to the investor is treated as FDI (Hausmann and Fernandez-Arias, 2000).

Considering the contribution of FDI in accomplishing economic growth, researchers and policymakers pursuit for the determinants' of FDIs. Even though many factors have been underlined as the determinants of FDI, FDI and financial literature regarding the impacts of financial development (FD) on FDI are relatively scarce.

Any increase of a country's financial assets in ratio to GDP is recognized as financial development (Islam et al., 2018). FD of a country can be captured by the spread of financial services, easing of difficulties to access and enjoy financial services by the people and increased reliability of the services (Liu et al., 2020). A country gains financial development when the financial instruments, markets, and intermediaries can confirm the effects of information availability, enforcement of laws, and reduce transactions costs and, therefore, do a correspondingly better job at providing the key functions of the financial sector in the economy. The main functions of a financial system are: (i) producing information about possible investments and allocate fund; (ii) monitoring investments and exerting corporate governance after providing finance; (iii) facilitating the trading, diversification, and management of risk; (iv) mobilizing and pooling savings; and (v) easing the exchange of goods and services (World Bank, 2020, Khan et al., 2020).

The research of Liu et al. (2020) and Islam et al. (2020) are more clear evidences that a developed financial system can positively contribute to FDI attractiveness of a country. However, the authors feel that a more

developed human capital (HC) can further enhance the impact of FD on FDI. HC is mostly recognized as the skill or capability of the people of the country; the labor force and/or the percentage of people's participation in the labor force. A skilled labor force is the greatest resource for a country. However, the effect of HC in moderating the impact of FD on FDI has rarely been explored. This research is a conscious effort to address the issue. Thus the research has several novelty points. Firstly, the research uses a novel proxy of FD, which is recognized as the most comprehensive FD proxy in recent literature. Secondly, it investigates the moderating effect of HC in FD-FDI relations. Thirdly, the research uses Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) countries as a sample for the experiment. BRI covers a wide and diverged range of countries which covers Asia, Europe, Africa and Latin America. It also covers countries form advanced economies, emerging market and low income country groups. Thus BRI sample is representative to the whole world.

The research finds profound evidences that development of financial sector significantly and positively affects FDI and a highly skilled labor force or human resource maneuvers the relationship in a positive way.

Section 3 of the research paper reviews the relevant literature. Section 4 describes the methods and materials used in the research. Section 5 presents the results found from analyses and relevant discussions. Finally, section 6 concludes the paper.

Literature Review

The significance of foreign direct investment has extensive effect in economic growth in developed and developing countries. If any country has a positive and steady growth, the country has the ability to attract the investors more, compared to a slower growth economies country. Studies conducted by Blomstrom et al. (1992) and Borensztein et al. (1998) pointed that FDI is positively associated with the economic growth of a nation. Coe et al. (1997) recognized a positive relationship between FDI and economic growth, and at the same time they suggested that host countries should have attained certain level of economic development which will ensure more securing the benefits of higher yield. Additionally, Liu et al. (2006) found evidence that greater economic growth charms

additional FDI inflows. Moreover, Mottaleb (2007) examined the relationship between FDI and economic growth, and showed that developing countries will be able to attract more FDI if they have more friendly business environment (e.g. easy rules for import and export, low tax and non-tax barriers) etc. for the investors and consistent economic growth. Another study, by Ljungwall and Li (2007), assessed the relationship between FDI and economic growth, considering the role of the financial sector in China, and showed a strongly significant positive association between FDI and economic growth. This result is similar to the findings of Hermes and Lensink (2003) and Alfaro et al. (2004). On the contrary, Carkovic and Levine (2005) examined the affiliation between FDI and economic growth, and pointed that FDI does not have any extra independent influence on economic growth on neither developed nor developing countries. Furthermore, Nonnemberg and de Mendonça (2004) conducted a study on china, and found that robust GDP growth can attract the inflow of FDI, but that FDI does not definitely contribute economic growth. Duasa (2007) showed no interconnection between FDI and economic growth in Malaysia, but recommended that FDI does contribute to the constancy of growth.

It is important for a country to attract more FDI whereas FD can exert a beneficial effect. A country's financial sector is considered to be developed when the financial instruments, markets, and intermediaries can confirm the effects of information availability, enforcement of laws, and reduce transactions costs and, therefore, do a correspondingly better job at providing the key functions of the financial sector in the economy. The main functions of a financial system are: (i) producing information about possible investments and allocate fund; (ii) monitoring investments and exerting corporate governance after providing finance; (iii) facilitating the trading, diversification, and management of risk; (iv) mobilizing and pooling savings; and (v) easing the exchange of goods and services (World_Bank, 2020, Khan et al., 2020).

A developed financial system mostly works as a sign of reliance to foreign investors (Liu et al., 2020). Predominantly, the financial system plays the role as an optimum resource distributor and cost minimization system, as well as information provider to the interested users (Jiang and Ma, 2019). Scholars come to an agreement that genuine sustainable benefit of

FDI will be accomplished when a host country has a developed, reliable, transparent financial system (Desbordes and Wei, 2017, Mahmood et al., 2018). A country with more developed financial system often experiences faster rate of economic growth and higher level of per capital income (Khan et al., 2020) and thus enjoy more economic freedom.

On the other hand, HC is considered as one of the most important absorptive capacities which can attract FDI projects. At the same time, FDI projects may also develop the human capital of the host country (Abdouli and Omri, 2020). Human capital of a country can be developed by proper education (Atiku et al., 2020) and development of necessary skills (Liu et al., 2020). While designing the education and training programs, the educators should consider the future requirements of MNCs which the learners are to grasp and acquire. As educated and skilled workforce are more likely to absorb the spillover effects of FDI, the country is expected to receive the maximum benefit form FDI projects while it has a developed human capital or work force (Islam et al., 2020, Hassan et al., 2016, Islam and Rana, 2012).

Materials and Methods

Variables and Data

We use stock of foreign direct investment inflows as a proxy for FDI since the stock value represents the total amount utilized in the host country (Liu et al., 2020). Financial sector development is a very complex matter and to be developed over the passage of time (Islam et al., 2019). Thus current account of FDI should not be a good match with long run financial development. Therefore, the existing body of empirical literature acknowledges the long run capability of stock of FDI to capture the scenario (Yeboua, 2019).

On the other hand, prior literature measures financial development with different bank based or market based proxies such as domestic credits provided to the private sector in ratio to GDP (Nkoa, 2018), domestic credit provided to private sector by banks and other financial institutions (Kutan et al., 2017), deposit money bank claims over deposit money bank and central bank claims (Otchere et al., 2016), liquid liabilities (Otchere et al., 2016), monetary aggregates such as narrow money and broad money (Nkoa, 2018), stock market capitalization in ratio to GDP (Hanif and Shariff, 2016), stock market turnover of

domestic shares (Sahin and Ege, 2015), stock value traded (Otchere et al., 2016), private bank credit over bank deposits (Bittencourt, 2012) etc. Some of the researchers endeavored to combine multiple proxies taking form banking sector indicators or stock market indicators or in combination of both using principal component analysis to make a better representation (Bittencourt, 2012). However, each of these measures have certain shortcomings and are subject to criticisms. Svirydzienka (2016) mentioned these traditional measure as obsolete as well, as it does not cover the multidimensionality of financial system and thus undermines the weight of financial system (Khan et al., 2019).

To avoid the complexity in representing financial sector, we proxy the sector with financial development index, initiated and developed by the International Monetary Fund (Sahay et al., 2016, Svirydzienka, 2016). The index is recently citing researchers' attraction and increasingly acknowledged as one of the best proxies for financial development (Liu et al., 2020, Khan et al., 2020, Islam et al., 2020, Islam et al., 2019) which combines 20 different dimensions of financial market comprising of banking and nonbanking financial institutional facts and financial market facts.

In line with previous literature, we use concerned control variables for example, "Human Capital"- as skilled labor force can make a country attractive to the foreign investors as a major source of absorptive capacity; Real GDP per capita as it is often used as a proxy for income level of the citizens and a higher purchasing power represents a wider market to the investors; Inflation (proxied by consumer price index) as it represents the macroeconomic stability of the host country; Domestic investment (proxied by gross fixed capital formation) as domestic investment and FDI work as complementary to each other; Openness to trade, computed as sum of export and import in ratio to GDP, as a country which is open to foreign trade is expected to formulate policies congenial to the foreign investors and protection of their investments; population (representative of market size) since large population is always representative of a large market size and by the number of population as largely populated countries are meant to have a better market base; Initial FDI as previous FDI trend most often impacts on future investment decision of the concerned investors since FDI is widely believed to be self-reinforcing, i.e. the previous investors,

if satisfied with the business environment of the host country, will tend to increase their investment and furthermore, new investors will be tempted in future years considering investments made by earlier investors as a proof of trust of good business environment (Liu et al., 2020, Islam et al., 2020, Islam et al., 2019).

The selection of sample countries is solely based on data availability and hence we use a panel data comprised of 79 countries for a time period from 1999 to 2017.

Empirical Strategy

This research is an extension of Liu et al. (2020) and thus we follow the basic theoretical framework of the authors and develop the following basic functional form which represents linear relation between FDI and FD.

$$FDI_{it} = f(I, FDI_{it}, FD_{it}, IQ_{it}, HC_{it}, RGDP_{it}, INFL_{it}, DI_{it}, TO_{it}, INFR_{it}, Pop_{it}) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

- FDI_{it} = Stock of inward foreign direct investment (FDI) per capita at county *i* and time *t*.
- I.FDI_{it} = Initial stock of inward FDI (FDI_{it-1}) per capita at country *i* and time *t*.
- FD_{it} = Financial development at county *i* and time *t*.
- IQ_{it} = Institutional Quality at country *i* at time *t*.
- HC_{it} = Human capital at country *i* at time *t*.
- RGDP_{it} = Gross domestic product at constant prices per capita at county *i* and time *t*.
- INFL_{it} = Inflation represented by consumer prices index at county *i* and time *t*.
- IQ_{it} = Domestic investment at county *i* and time *t*.
- DI_{it} = Openness to trade at county *i* and time *t*.
- TO_{it} = Infrastructure at county *i* and time *t*.
- Pop_{it} = Population at county *i* and time *t*.

To control the large variances among the observations of different variables, those are taken into logarithmic form other than those in percentage and ratio form. This specific research extends Liu et al. (2020) by investigating the moderating effect of trade openness in FD-FDI connection. We follow the literature (for example, Aibai et al., 2019, Agbloyor et al., 2014) and for interaction term of TO with FD to examine the moderating effect. Thus considering our research objectives, variables and the moderating effects our research model can be written as:

$$\ln FDI_{it} = I. \ln FDI_{it} + FD_{it} + FD_{it} * IQ_{it} + IQ_{it}$$

$$HC_{it} + \ln RGDP_{it} + \ln INFL_{it} + \ln DI_{it} + \ln TO_{it} + \ln INFR_{it} + \ln Pop_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

In the above equation 'ln' refers to the logarithmic form of variables in appropriate cases and 'FD_{it} * TO_{it}' stands for the moderating effect of TO which is otherwise called as interaction term.

The research data comes from a panel of countries consisting of 79 BRI countries from the year 1999 to 2017. The countries and time span are selected based upon availability of data. To analyze the data, we employ fixed effect (FE) and random effect (RE) modelling. Most often panel data is considered to have low level of biasness due to large number of data points which raise the degree of freedom increased ability to study the dynamics (Hsiao, 1995). We estimate equation (2) with FE and RE. Moreover, to gain confidence of the findings we additionally employ feasible least square (FGLS).

Although panel data estimation raised data points, the inference of it is sensitive to specification of the model and used methodology (Kittel and Winner, 2005). The panel data estimation is not appropriate to be estimated with usual OLS estimator (Vuko and Čular, 2014, Wooldridge, 2012) while Pooled OLS technique can be used as it allows clusters or group settings.

However, a pooled OLS technique may not be efficient to estimate a heterogeneous panel as it ignores cross section specific effects. For such reasons some basic assumptions for example, orthogonality may be violated. Furthermore, it is acknowledged that OLS estimation is prone to heteroscedasticity in case of pooled time series and/or cross-sectional settings (Al Nasser and Gomez, 2009, Al Nasser, 2007, Jones and Manuelli, 2005). It is because that the intercept is restricted to become identical due to pooling of data. Thus application of pooled OLS ignores the cross-sectional heterogeneity and considers the intercept as $\beta_{it} = \beta$.

Fixed and Random effect modeling (FE and RE) can ease the limitations of pooled OLS to a certain extent. While the panel have a large cross section the FE and RE techniques are especially effective. The current research considers primarily 79 countries from BRI (OBOR) region. Moreover, our panel contains heterogeneity as it contains economies from divergent location, development stages, infrastructure, population and inter alia. In such a case an unrestricted

intercept is more plausible (Hassan, 2003). Following are the general specification for fixed and random effect model-

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{k=i}^k \alpha_k X_{kit} + \varepsilon_i + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Here ε_i measures cross section specific and represents the general disturbance term. To be more specific the fixed effect and random effect models can be specified respectively as follows:

$$Y_{it} = (\alpha_0 + u_i) + \sum_{k=i}^k \alpha_k X_{kit} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{k=i}^k \alpha_k X_{kit} + (\varepsilon_i + \mu_{it}) \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

The fixed effect model examines the difference between country-specific intercepts, and the random effect model estimates the variance components by groups (or time) and the error term. The slopes of K-vector are assumed to be unchanged in either of the models. The Hausman test makes a comparison between fixed and random effect models. While the null of the Hausman test is "difference in coefficients not systematic." A significant chi-square leads to the rejection of the null and acceptance of fixed effect model and vice versa. Additionally, FGLS can control the potential autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity and cross sectional dependency (Le et al., 2016, Motelle and Biekpe, 2015).

Results

Descriptive statistics and correlation matrix

Descriptive statistics gives an overview of the data and thus it is important to look into the descriptive statistics of the original variables before we start analyzing the data. Facing Table 1 represents descriptive statistics for current study, whereas Table 2 presents the correlation matrix of the variables. The descriptive statistics shows that in Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) sample countries the mean stock of FDI inflow is approximately \$59000 million whereas the minimum and maximum stock of FDI are found to be \$4.420 and \$1490,000 million respectively with a standard deviation of \$13700 million. The key explanatory variable, FD, is an index, the value of which ranges from 0 to 1. In case of BRI countries, the mean FD is found to be 0.3267 whereas the minimum and maximum ranges are 0.0299 and 0.8592 with a standard deviation of 0.1859. The number of observations, at maximum is 1501 which is comprised

of 79 countries' data for 19 years. For some variables a very few observations are missing which made the panel unbalanced. Furthermore, each pair of the variables, as found from the correlation matrix, are having significant correlation between them. As we focus more on the dependent and the key explanatory variable we find a positive correlation of 72% ($p < 0.01$). For other pairs the correlation coefficients are found to be below 80% which gives us an assurance of the variables to be free from multicollinearity (Rahman et al., 2017, Gujarati, 2009).

Table-1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
FDI	1501	59000,000,000	13700,000,000	4,420,000	1490,000,000,000
FD	1501	0.3267	0.1859	0.0299	0.8592
HC_emp	1501	56.0685	11.8701	30.601	87.818
GDPpc	1501	10200	12300	273.8509	62800
INFL	1465	93.1659	30.0592	13.2942	337.104
DI	1488	23.3367	7.0957	0.2929	68.0227
TO	1498	88.0655	47.54	20.7225	441.6038
INFR	1498	18.1858	14.9163	0.073	65.2985
Pop	1501	45,300,000	151,000,000	97600	1,390,000,000

Table-2: Correlation Matrix

	lnFDI	FDx	HC_emp	lnRGDPpc	lnINFL	lnDI	lnTO	INFR	lnPop	lnHC_life
lnFDI	1									
FDx	0.720***	1								
HC_emp	-0.151***	-0.139***	1							
lnRGDPpc	0.565***	0.791***	-0.169***	1						
lnINFL	0.337***	0.213***	0.00197	0.200***	1					
lnDI	0.0599**	0.0890***	0.0534**	0.0524**	0.110***	1				
lnTO	0.00634	0.155***	0.0617**	0.243***	0.0313	0.148***	1			
INFR	0.457***	0.700***	-0.272***	0.713***	0.0743***	0.0658**	0.229***	1		
lnPop	0.561***	0.175***	-0.0296	-0.183***	-0.0142	-0.0172	-0.471***	-0.166***	1	
lnHC_life	0.417***	0.588***	-0.195***	0.688***	0.258***	0.236***	0.274***	0.710***	-0.166***	1

Note: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Financial development (FD) and foreign direct investment (FDI)- moderating effect of human capital (HC)- Baseline estimations

This research investigates the role of FD in attracting FDI while also considering the moderating effect of TO. We estimate the relationship based on data from a panel of countries from BRI region. Table 3 presents the baseline estimation in this regard. For the estimation, fixed and random effect modeling has been used while either of these two is to be chosen based on Hausman test. Column 1 and 3 present results from fixed effect model and column 2 and 4 present results from random effect model. Moreover, FGLS is used to support the findings which is presented in column 5. Columns 3 to 5 includes the moderation effect represented by FD and human capital interaction term whereas column 1 and 2 present results without the interaction term. Between fixed and random effect models, for both of the cases (with and without moderation effect) fixed effect models have been proven as most appropriate based on Hausman test as presented in Table 4. The models show a significant and positive effect of FD (as represented by FDx) on FDI. We can also notice that FD gains higher significance ($p < 0.01$) and higher coefficients while the moderation effect is considered in comparison to models in which the moderation effect is not considered. It means that while an economy is more concentrating on human capital development, the development of financial sector of that economy comes with more efficiency to attract more FDI. The

interaction terms in models 3 to 5, we also find highly significant ($p < 0.01$) and positive coefficients which prove an effective moderation mechanism in the sample economies. The human capital variable (measured as “HC_ emp) itself is also positive and significant in all alternative specifications which further reminds the emergence of TO in this regard. Other controlling variables are also found to be positive and significant which are as per economic theories. However, FE models may be biased due to presence of autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity and cross sectional dependency. We further go for FGLS which is capable of controlling the said issues and the result out of FGLS is presented in column 5. The findings are in line with the FE results.

Table-3: Financial development and FDI- moderating role of trade openness-baseline estimation

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Without moderation effect		With moderation effect		
	FE	RE	FE	RE	FGLS
l.lnFDI	0.1416*** (0.0128)	0.4669*** (0.0156)	0.1399*** (0.0127)	0.4601*** (0.0156)	0.5332*** (0.0154)
FDx	0.8247** (0.2962)	0.4570** (0.2057)	6.8980*** (2.2286)	3.2300*** (1.0334)	2.7410*** (0.9308)
HC_ emp	0.0940 (0.0716)	-0.0557** (0.0222)	0.5371*** (0.1763)	0.1350* (0.0733)	0.1118* (0.0659)
lnRGDPpc	0.4735*** (0.0897)	0.4673*** (0.0315)	0.5252*** (0.0915)	0.4882*** (0.0323)	0.4319*** (0.0297)
lnINFL	0.5137*** (0.0534)	0.3664*** (0.0718)	0.4984*** (0.0536)	0.3730*** (0.0714)	0.3459*** (0.0738)
lnDI	0.0746*** (0.0085)	0.0115 (0.0089)	0.0759*** (0.0085)	0.0152* (0.0090)	0.0058 (0.0086)
lnTO	0.1751*** (0.0662)	0.5320*** (0.0452)	0.1667** (0.0661)	0.5653*** (0.0468)	0.5363*** (0.0432)
INFR	0.0189 (0.0230)	0.0488*** (0.0160)	0.0196 (0.0230)	0.0497*** (0.0160)	0.0418*** (0.0146)
lnPop	0.8823*** (0.1510)	0.5149*** (0.0187)	0.9851*** (0.1552)	0.5262*** (0.0190)	0.4665*** (0.0180)
FDx * HC_ emp			0.8163*** (0.2969)	0.3826*** (0.1400)	0.3284*** (0.1261)
Cons	-3.0476 (2.7673)	-3.7817*** (0.5749)	-8.3434** (3.3661)	-5.5794*** (0.8728)	-5.2656*** (0.8112)
Obs.	1455	1455	1455	1455	1455
Year Dummy	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
GroupWise heteroscedasticity					
Chi2	8630.55***	-	8878.08***	-	11929.61***

Standard errors are in parenthesis; *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table-4: Hausman test and Wooldridge test results for the models

Hausman test for model 1 & 2 (H0: Random Effect is appropriate)	Chi2	825.24
	P value	0.0000
Hausman test for model 3 & 4 (H0: Random Effect is appropriate)	Chi2	820.70
	P value	0.0000
Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data (H0: no first-order autocorrelation)	Chi2	218.624
	P value	0.0000

Robustness checking

As we consider human capital to be one of the most important moderators of FD-FDI relations, we felt necessity to check the robustness of the results found in baseline estimations. To check the robustness of our findings we replace our baseline HC variable with an alternative one. Thus we replace employment ratio by life expectancy at birth as an alternative proxy of HC and investigate the relations once again. The alternative proxy is also frequently used in literature (Sultanuzzaman et al., 2019, Islam et al., 2018) and the relevant data comes from WDI (2019). We retained the similar methodologies and techniques to re-estimate relations. The results are presented in table 5.

We find the results presented in Table 5 in a similar and comparable manner with Table 3, while columns 1, 3 and 5 are our key focus in presenting the results of FE modelling without and with the moderation effect and FGLS model respectively. The results of our robustness check exercise are very similar to our baseline estimations in terms of sign and significance. Most importantly we find the FD variable is showing highly positive and significant coefficients and the alternative human capital variable is showing insignificant coefficient while the moderation effect is not considered and showing highly significant ($p < 0.01$) and positive coefficients while the moderation effect is duly regarded. Moreover, the moderation term itself is also positive and significant. All these indicate that the findings are in line with the baseline estimations and deserve adequate generalizability.

Table-5: Financial development and FDI- moderating role of trade openness-robustness check

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Without moderation effect		With moderation effect		
	FE	RE	FE	RE	FGLS
l.lnFDI	0.1437*** (0.0128)	0.4682*** (0.0156)	0.1470*** (0.0128)	0.4603*** (0.0155)	0.5347*** (0.0154)
FDx	0.8209*** (0.2964)	0.4303** (0.2058)	31.7594*** (7.7212)	16.8027*** (3.8945)	14.8676*** (3.5310)
HC_life	0.1795 (0.5067)	-0.2122 (0.2302)	2.4553*** (0.7589)	1.4408*** (0.4558)	1.3103*** (0.4169)
lnRGDPpc	0.4805*** (0.0908)	0.4686*** (0.0320)	0.4459*** (0.0907)	0.4772*** (0.0321)	0.4199*** (0.0294)
lnINFL	0.5015*** (0.0544)	0.3705*** (0.0720)	0.4721*** (0.0546)	0.3584*** (0.0714)	0.3394*** (0.0738)
lnDI	0.0757*** (0.0085)	0.0122 (0.0092)	0.0712*** (0.0085)	0.0096 (0.0092)	0.0007 (0.0088)
lnTO	0.1749*** (0.0673)	0.5265*** (0.0454)	0.1751*** (0.0669)	0.5275*** (0.0454)	0.5003*** (0.0417)
INFR	0.0165 (0.0230)	0.0644*** (0.0168)	0.0053 (0.0230)	0.0707*** (0.0169)	0.0611*** (0.0155)
lnPop	0.8999*** (0.1559)	0.5152*** (0.0188)	0.7463*** (0.1597)	0.5188*** (0.0187)	0.4592*** (0.0178)
FDx * HC_life			7.2532*** (1.8088)	3.8099*** (0.9054)	3.3822*** (0.8209)
Cons	-3.4534 (3.0174)	-3.3801*** (1.0275)	-10.0859*** (3.4264)	-10.3369*** (1.9465)	-9.7032*** (1.7960)
Obs.	1455	1455	1455	1455	1455
Year Dummy	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Standard errors are in parenthesis; *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

The overall findings, though, are to some extent different from Liu et al. (2020) and Islam et al. (2020), are meaningful and are of significant value to the researchers and policy makers. With a similar sample the Liu et al. (2020) generally find that human capital has a negative impact in attracting FDI. Islam et al. (2020), though, considered the moderation effect of institutional quality, the relation of HC remained similar. The authors contended the potential of under skilled labor market in sample countries to cause so. However, it is noticeable that the authors ignored the moderation role of HC with FD, which is covered in our research. It means that negative effect of HC in attracting FDI, as identified in prior literature, can be overcome if the policymakers consider to develop both of human capital and financial sector of a country simultaneously.

Concluding remarks

The importance of attracting FDIs is becoming increasingly vital for the struggling underdeveloped and developing countries for ensuring economic prosperity (Liu et al., 2020, Islam et al., 2020), as FDI come not only in the form of money but also in the forms of developed technologies, efficient management and better knowledge which can bring spillover effect over domestic firms and benefits the country. This research endeavors to empirically reveal the effect of financial development to make the host countries attractive to MNCs and the moderating role of human capital. At the baseline, human capital is proxied by employment ratio of the people of a country.

The research considers a novel proxy of financial development, financial development index, developed by the IMF (2019) and recognized by the recent researchers as capable to represent financial sector more comprehensively than any traditional proxy (Islam et al., 2019, Islam et al., 2018). The index considers a number of indicators of financial sector-financial market and financial institutions and combines together into a single index.

The researchers considered a sample of 79 BRI partner countries. The major reason to consider BRI partner countries are many-fold, such as the partnership is a mega project after the Marshal plan which is going to integrate the countries economically, financially and commercially. Moreover, the Belt and the Road network are covering a large and diversified area of the world – Asia, Europe, Africa and Latin America

while the countries are at different development stages such as advanced markets, emerging markets and low income countries. Thus the BRI sample is considered as global representative which makes this study a novel one. One more novelty is the investigation of human capital moderating effect in FD-FDI relationship which is still ignored in literature.

The study applies fixed - random effect modeling and FGLS modeling. Applying dataset from 1999 to 2017, the research concludes that the previous finding in literature, that is, human capital is negatively correlated to FDI attraction in BRI countries (Liu et al., 2020, Islam et al., 2020), takes a different direction. It is because this research considered the moderating effect of HC which was unnoticed by prior researchers. To check the robustness of the findings, the human capital proxy is replaced with life expectancy at birth which is also a widely used proxy of human capital. In robustness checking the results are found to be highly consistent to baseline estimations in terms of sign and significance. Thus this research argues that the findings as stronger than before and generalizable for future decision making. The research suggests the policy makers to concentrate both on financial development and human capital development so that these two ingredients can make the countries more attractive to MNCs to divert their investments into these countries.

This research adds a lot to the theoretical literature by unearthing the contribution of one important moderating factor, human capital to realize the impact of FD on FDI, which was undiscovered in previous literature. In practice, it guides the future researchers to identify the FD scenario more comprehensively than before. It guides the policymakers to work more to develop human capital of a country rather than taking large population as a burden. Future FDI attraction and the resultant economic growth of the host country is expected to be positively guided by human capital and financial development.

Despite all these contributions of the research, there remains some definite limitations. It considers financial system as a whole and ignores analyzing the impacts of separate parts in FDI attraction. Moreover, it takes FDI as a whole as well and ignores the different types of FDI to be attracted by FD. Future researchers should take the scope and cover the gaps to make the issues clearer and guide the policymakers.

References

- Abdouli, M. & Omri, A. 2020. Exploring the nexus among FDI inflows, environmental quality, human capital, and economic growth in the Mediterranean region. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1-23.
- Agbloyor, E. K., Abor, J. Y., Adjasi, C. K. D. & Yawson, A. 2014. Private capital flows and economic growth in Africa: The role of domestic financial markets. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 30, 137-152.
- Aibai, A., Huang, X., Luo, Y. & Peng, Y. 2019. Foreign Direct Investment, Institutional Quality, and Financial Development along the Belt and Road: An Empirical Investigation. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 1-20.
- Al Nasser, O. M. 2007. The Determinants of the U.S. Foreign Direct Investment: Does the Region Matter? *Global Economic Review*, 36, 37-51.
- Al Nasser, O. M. & Gomez, X. G. 2009. Do well-functioning financial systems affect the FDI flows to Latin America. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 29, 60-75.
- Alfaro, L., Chanda, A., Kalemli-Ozcan, S. & Sayek, S. 2004. FDI and economic growth: the role of local financial markets. *Journal of international economics*, 64, 89-112.
- Atiku, S. O., Lawal, I. O. & Gamede, V. 2020. Human Capital Development and Faculty Members' Contributions. *The Journal of Accounting and Management*, 10.
- Bittencourt, M. 2012. Financial development and economic growth in Latin America: Is Schumpeter right? *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 34, 341-355.
- Blomstrom, M., Lipsey, R. E. & Zejan, M. 1992. What explains developing country growth? : National bureau of economic research.
- Borensztein, E., De Gregorio, J. & Lee, J.-W. 1998. How does foreign direct investment affect economic growth? *Journal of international Economics*, 45, 115-135.
- Carkovic, M. & Levine, R. 2005. Does foreign direct investment accelerate economic growth? In: MORAN, T. H., GRAHAM, E. M. & BLOMSTROM, M. (eds.) *Does foreign direct investment promote development*.
- Coe, D. T., Helpman, E. & Hoffmaister, A. W. 1997. North-south R & D spillovers. *The Economic Journal*, 107, 134-149.
- De Gregorio, J. 2005. The role of foreign direct investment and natural resources in economic development. *Multinationals and Foreign Investment in Economic Development*. Springer.
- Desbordes, R. & Wei, S.-J. 2017. The effects of financial development on foreign direct investment. *Journal of Development Economics*, 127, 153-168.
- Duasa, J. 2007. Malaysian foreign direct investment and growth: does stability matter? *Journal of Economic Cooperation Among Islamic Countries*, 28.
- Gujarati, D. N. 2009. *Basic econometrics*, New York, NY, USA, Tata McGraw-Hill Education.
- Hanif, A. & Shariff, S. S. M. Relationship Between Foreign Direct Investment and Financial Development. *Proceedings of the 1st AAGBS International Conference on Business Management 2014 (AiCoBM 2014)*, 2016. Springer, 457-467.
- Hassan, M. K. FDI, information technology and economic growth in the MENA region. 2003. Citeseer.
- Hassan, M. R., Das, P. C. & Islam, M. A. 2016. Per Capita GDP And Population Growth Nexus: Facts from a Cross Country Analysis. *The Cost and Management*, 44, 39-43.
- Hausmann, R. & Fernandez-Arias, E. 2000. Foreign direct investment: good cholesterol?
- Hermes, N. & Lensink, R. 2003. Foreign direct investment, financial development and economic growth. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 40, 142-163.
- Hsiao, W. C. 1995. Abnormal economics in the health sector. *Health policy*, 32, 125-139.
- IMF 2019. Financial Development Index Database. In: IMF, T. (ed.).
- Islam, M. A., Hassan, M. R. & Rana, M. 2019. Financial Deepening, Foreign Direct Investment and Economic growth: an ARDL Approach Evidence from Bangladesh. *The Jahangirnagar Journal of Business Studies*, 8, 169-190.
- Islam, M. A., Khan, M. A., Popp, J., Sroka, W. & Oláh, J. 2020. Financial Development and Foreign Direct Investment—The Moderating Role of Quality Institutions. *Sustainability*, 12, 3556.
- Islam, M. A., Liu, H., Khan, M. A., Reza, S. M., Yahia, Y. E. & Nasrin, L. 2018. Causal Relationship between Economic Growth, Financial Deepening, Foreign Direct Investment and Innovation: Evidence from China. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 8, 1086-1101.
- Islam, M. A. & Rana, S. 2012. Service Quality of Banks: A comparative Study of Public and Private Sector in Greater Mymensingh. *Journal of Nazrul University*, 1, 164-180.
- Jiang, C. & Ma, X. 2019. The Impact of Financial Development on Carbon Emissions: A Global Perspective. *Sustainability*, 11, 5241.
- Jones, L. E. & Manuelli, R. E. 2005. Chapter 1 Neoclassical Models of Endogenous Growth: The Effects of Fiscal Policy, Innovation and Fluctuations. In: AGHION, P. & DURLAUF, S. N. (eds.) *Handbook of Economic Growth*. Elsevier.
- Khan, M. A., Islam, M. A. & Akbar, U. 2020. Do economic freedom matters for finance in developing economies: a panel threshold analysis. *Applied Economics Letters*, 1-4.
- Khan, M. A., Khan, M. A., Abdulahi, M. E., Liaqat, I. & Shah, S. S. H. 2019. Institutional quality and financial development: The United States perspective. *Journal of Multinational Financial Management*.
- Kittel, B. & Winner, H. 2005. How reliable is pooled analysis in political economy? *The globalization welfare state nexus revisited*. *European Journal of Political Research*, 44, 269-293.
- Kutan, A. M., Samargandi, N. & Sohag, K. 2017. Does Institutional

- Quality Matter for Financial Development and Growth? Further Evidence from MENA Countries. *Australian Economic Papers*, 56, 228-248.
- Le, T.-H., Kim, J. & Lee, M. 2016. Institutional Quality, Trade Openness, and Financial Sector Development in Asia: An Empirical Investigation. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 52, 1047-1059.
- Liu, H., Islam, M. A., Khan, M. A., Md Ismail, H. & Pervaiz, K. 2020. Does financial deepening attract foreign direct investment? Fresh evidence from panel threshold analysis. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 101198.
- Liu, L.-g., Chow, K. & Li, U. 2006. Determinants of foreign direct investment in East Asia: Did China crowd out FDI from her developing East Asian neighbours.
- Ljungwall, C. & Li, J. 2007. Financial sector development, FDI and economic growth in China. China Center for Economic Research.
- Mahmood, H., Furqan, M. & Bagais, O. A. 2018. Environmental Accounting of Financial Development and Foreign Investment: Spatial Analyses of East Asia. *Sustainability*, 11, 13.
- Motelle, S. & Biekpe, N. 2015. Financial integration and stability in the Southern African development community. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 79, 100-117.
- Mottaleb, K. A. 2007. Determinants of foreign direct investment and its impact on economic growth in developing countries.
- Nkoa, B. E. O. 2018. Determinants of foreign direct investment in Africa: An analysis of the impact of financial development. *Economics Bulletin*, 38, 221-233.
- Nonnemberg, M. B. & de Mendonça, M. J. C. The determinants of foreign direct investment in developing countries. *Anais do XXXII Encontro Nacional de Economia [Proceedings of the 32nd Brazilian Economics Meeting]*, 2004. ANPEC-Associação Nacional dos Centros de Pós-Graduação em ...
- Otchere, I., Soumaré, I. & Yourougou, P. 2016. FDI and financial market development in Africa. *The World Economy*, 39, 651-678.
- Rahman, M. M., Ashraf, B. N., Zheng, C. & Begum, M. 2017. Impact of Cost Efficiency on Bank Capital and the Cost of Financial Intermediation: Evidence from BRICS Countries. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 5, 32.
- Sahay, M. R., Cihak, M., N'Diaye, M. P. M., Barajas, M. A., Pena, M. D. B. A., Bi, R., Gao, M., Kyobe, M. A. J. & Nguyen, L. 2016. Rethinking financial deepening: Stability and growth in emerging markets. *International Monetary Fund*.
- Sahin, S. & Ege, I. 2015. Financial Development and FDI in Greece and Neighbouring Countries: A Panel Data Analysis. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 24, 583-588.
- Sultanuzzaman, M. R., Fan, H., Mohamued, E. A., Hossain, M. I. & Islam, M. A. 2019. Effects of export and technology on economic growth: Selected emerging Asian economies. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 32, 2515-2531.
- Svirydzhenka, K. 2016. Introducing a new broad-based index of financial development. *IMF Working Paper*, WP/16/5.
- Vuko, T. & Čular, M. 2014. Finding determinants of audit delay by pooled OLS regression analysis. *Croatian Operational Research Review*, 5, 81-91.
- WDI 2019. *World Development Indicators*.
- Wooldridge, J. 2012. Multiple regression analysis: Further issues. *Introductory econometrics: A modern approach*, 196-198.
- World_Bank 2020. *Global Financial Development Report 2019/2020: Bank Regulation and Supervision a Decade After the Global Financial Crisis*, World Bank Group.
- Yahia, Y. E., Haiyun, L., Khan, M. A., Shah, S. S. H. & Islam, M. A. 2018. The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Domestic Investment: Evidence from Sudan. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 8, 11-20.
- Yeboua, K. 2019. Foreign direct investment, financial development and economic growth in Africa: evidence from threshold modeling. *Transnational Corporations Review*, 11, 187-189.